

The Reliability of Wireless Sensor Network

Authors : Bohuslava Juhasova, Igor Halenar, Martin Juhas

Abstract : The wireless communication is one of the widely used methods of data transfer at the present days. The benefit of this communication method is the partial independence of the infrastructure and the possibility of mobility. In some special applications it is the only way how to connect. This paper presents some problems in the implementation of a sensor network connection for measuring environmental parameters in the area of manufacturing plants.

Keywords : network, communication, reliability, sensors

Conference Title : ICCSET 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Technology

Conference Location : Toronto, Canada

Conference Dates : June 16-17, 2014